

The NEPHELE Meta-Orchestration Approach for Distributed Applications in the Computing Continuum

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Abstract. Following the trend for the provision of applications over programmable resources distributed across the computing continuum, in this manuscript, we detail a novel meta-orchestration approach for management of such applications. Two main challenges are considered. The first challenge regards the management of Internet of Things (IoT) interoperability and convergence aspects with edge and cloud computing infrastructure. The second challenge regards the development of synergistic orchestration mechanisms that can facilitate the management of distributed applications across multi-cluster infrastructure.

Keywords: Meta-orchestration · Virtual Object · Computing Continuum

1 Introduction

The rapid advancement of next-generation Internet of Things (IoT) and Edge computing technologies has led to the emergence of a highly interconnected and complex digital landscape. Two key challenges emerge in this transition. The first challenge involves the need to unify IoT technologies through innovative architectural approaches that ensure interoperability across existing and emerging solutions, models, and devices. The second challenge lies in establishing an integrated meta-orchestration framework for Hyper-Distributed Applications (HDAs), facilitating collaboration between Cloud and Edge orchestration platforms [1]. This synergy is essential to optimize end-to-end application deployment and efficient data management across the entire computing continuum.

The NEPHELE project [2] is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) project that aims to provide effective orchestration of applications deployed across a diverse range of computing resources across the IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum,

spanning from low-resource IoT nodes to far-Edge processing and powerful multi-Cloud environments. In this paper, we present the key software artifacts of the NEPHELE project. We focus on the key following components:

VOStack: The VOStack is a software stack that enables the creation of Virtual Objects (VOs) as virtual counterparts of IoT devices. It provides a set of abstractions that facilitate the management of any IoT device through a virtualized instance while enhancing its capabilities with a multi-layer software stack. It equips VOs with essential edge computing and IoT functionalities, including distributed data management and analysis leveraging machine learning (ML) and digital twinning techniques.

Synergetic MetaOrchestrator (SMO): The SMO undertakes the role of the efficient coordination, management, deployment, and orchestration of distributed computing and network resources across the continuum. Aiming to provide a synergetic solution for multi-cloud orchestration, the SMO relies on the effective synergy of multi-cluster resource orchestration and network orchestration across the continuum, thus providing a holistic approach to managing resources.

Dashboard & Development Environment: The Dashboard and Development Environment constitute the entry point into the NEPHELE SMO framework from a software development perspective and from a deployment management perspective. NEPHELE introduces a developer-centric sandbox, built on the GitLab IDE and CI/CD framework, for end-to-end artifact development. Additionally, we present the HDA Registry, which enables storage, distribution, and verification of all deployment-related artifacts.

2 NEPHELE Architecture

In this section, we thoroughly describe the NEPHELE approach for orchestrating distributed applications in the cloud continuum. The hierarchical framework is designed to navigate and streamline the above-defined challenges. As shown in Fig. 1, the main components of the architecture are:

- Dashboard and Development Environment: This component hosts the set of developed hyper-distributed applications, (c)VOs, and the user-defined application graphs and intents.
- Synergetic MetaOrchestrator (SMO): This is the main component of the NEPHELE architecture and is responsible for the overall orchestration of the hyper-distributed applications over the available infrastructure
- Network Resource Manager: This component is responsible for network management functionalities across the compute continuum.
- Multi-Cluster Resource Manager: This component is responsible for having an overall view of the available computing resources across the continuum. It manages multi-cluster resources based on proper resource abstraction.
- Edge/Cloud Resource Managers: These components are responsible for managing the deployment part and life-cycle of applications in the edge and cloud clusters respectively.

Fig. 1. NEPHELE Architecture Overview

- VOSTack: The VO is considered to be the virtual counterpart/extension of an IoT device into the network infrastructure, also here we include the functionalities of the IoT software stack (VOSTack).

2.1 Dashboard and Development Environment

The Development Environment and the Dashboard form a cohesive ecosystem that supports the entire lifecycle of Hyper-Distributed Applications (HDAs). The Development Environment guides the conception, creation, and validation of HDAs through the HDA Registry and a set of development tools and documentation under open container standards (OCI). Simultaneously, the Dashboard centralizes monitoring of the NEPHELE infrastructure, offering real-time visibility into system health and performance, and acting as a hub for intent-based orchestration. This environment is composed by the next core components:

Sandbox Repository: hosted on Eclipse GitLab, it consolidates development documentation for HDAs and the SMO framework. This repository is augmented by a Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery (CI/CD) pipeline that automates artifact creation and validation, and includes a ready-to-use examples in the form of a demo end-to-end HDA.

HDA Registry (HDAR): central to this component, serves as the primary storage and distribution mechanism for all HDA-related artifacts, including Docker images, Helm charts, Network Functions (NF) and custom descriptors. Integrated with the SMO, the HDAR supports OCI and manages public

and private repositories under a unified Authentication and Authorization (AA) framework.

Graph Descriptor (HDAG): as conceptualization of HDA, outlines the chain of distributed services forming the application in the context of NEPHELE. The HDAG incorporates inter-service links and intent-based orchestration, enabling the SMO to place services efficiently along the computing continuum.

Command-line tool (hdarctl): to streamline developer interactions with the HDAR this utility supports key tasks such as creating baseline artifacts (HDAG, cVO, NF), performing lint checks to validate syntax and structure, and pushing or pulling artifacts to and from the HDAR.

HDA Verification (HDAV): the component incorporates artifact verification and scanning procedures. The HDAR runs security and consistency checks—ranging from vulnerability scans (CVEs) to digital signature validation—before making artifacts available to the SMO.

2.2 SMO

The SMO is responsible for orchestrating the deployment and lifecycle management of distributed applications over programmable resources in the computing continuum. It takes deployment requests via the dashboard, formulates deployment plans based on infrastructure status and user-defined requirements, and continuously monitors the system to trigger optimizations when necessary. The SMO interacts with the multi-cluster resource manager and the network resource manager to ensure efficient resource utilization. The following are the key functional components of the SMO:

Intent Manager: to allow developers to express high-level requirements without specific technical details, we utilize intents. The user-defined requirements are mapped to actual resources with an intent translation mechanism.

Deployment Planner: at the SMO level, the application requirements submitted as intents, are processed to formulate a deployment plan, which, essentially, determines the requirements for an application graph deployment. Specifically, we consider that the intent requirements are mapped into specific categories for each application node, e.g., (i) computational resources, (ii) memory resources, (iii) number of replicas, and (iv) network constraints.

Re-optimization Engine (compute/network): this component interacts with the Network Resource Manager and the Multi-Cluster Resource Manager to query the availability in terms of network and computing resources and dictate the required actions to satisfy the application requirements and facilitate the infrastructure management. Specifically, the Re-optimization Engine is responsible for triggering the Network Resource Manager to expand or scale down the NEPHELE infrastructure according to the current state and needs of the infrastructure.

AI-assisted Synergetic Optimization Engine: This component is responsible for triggering different levels of synergy between the layers of NEPHELE architecture based on events. Following the principle of the system of systems, the SMO monitors (i) the entire NEPHELE infrastructure (compute/network)

and (ii) specific performance metrics of the application graphs and triggers various events that enable the synergy between the components of the architecture.

Centralized Monitoring Engine: the SMO monitors the NEPHELE infrastructure and during the lifetime of the application, the SMO collects metrics from the deployed resources, the respective traffic metrics, and the performance metrics of the application nodes, which are stored in a centralized monitoring system (e.g. Prometheus).

2.3 Network Resource Manager

The Network Resource Manager is responsible for managing network resources and functionalities across the edge-cloud compute continuum and ensuring network performance guarantees for distributed application deployments. The Network Resource Manager undertakes the identification of the computing and network resources and the setup of the related cluster topology, by instantiating network slices according to the QoS requirements of the considered application, followed by the management of their lifecycle, while encompassing processes for the ongoing optimization of network resource utilization. The key functionalities of the Network Resource Manager are:

Network Slice Lifecycle Management: is responsible for the creation, deployment, monitoring, and termination of network slices.

VPN tunneling: establishes secure and encrypted communication channels over public networks, enabling private connectivity between distributed clusters. Through VPN tunneling, the Network Resource Manager ensures the integrity, and authentication of data transmitted between distributed clusters, safeguarding sensitive information against unauthorized access or interception.

Network Resources Optimization Engine: continuously monitors, analyzes, and optimizes network resource utilization. It orchestrates the efficient allocation and management of network resources by dynamically adjusting network configurations, routing policies, and bandwidth allocation to enhance performance, reliability, and efficiency.

Infrastructure Scaling: in scenarios where infrastructure scaling is required, the Network Resource Manager seamlessly integrates with Virtualized Infrastructure Manager and Resource Orchestration frameworks like OpenStack and Kubernetes, to facilitate seamless expansion or contraction of the utilized resources.

2.4 Multi-Cluster Resource Manager

The Multi-Cluster Manager oversees the management of computational resources across multiple Edge/Cloud clusters. This component operates under the assumption that various clusters are integrated into a unified continuum. It manages multiple (Kubernetes-based) clusters across diverse environments and providers, offering a centralized and unified interface for administration and operation.

Placement Optimization Engine: it acts as an Integrated mechanism of the Multi-Cluster Manager to guarantee the application requirements with efficient resource utilization among the involved clusters. As a result, concerning the

intent acting as a constraint this optimization mechanism decides the appropriate Cluster to be deployed depending on the availability, the requested resources (e.g., CPU, memory, GPU), and the network constraints (e.g., bandwidth, collocation constraints), for each application node of the application graph.

Centralized Security Mechanism: this component is known as the ‘Issuer’ in the security architecture and acts as the trusted entity for issuing the Verifiable Credentials (VCs) using the OpenID Connect for Credential Issuance (OIDC4CI).

VO Discovery Server: This component stores all necessary information about the instantiated VOs and the respective devices that the VOs represent. Specifically, the description of the device, the cluster where the VO is deployed, the IPs, and all necessary information and metadata (e.g., communication protocols). As VOs can be part of more than one application graph, this component is responsible for communicating with the placement optimization engine for the above-mentioned information and also facilitates the operations of a Centralized Security Mechanism for secure communication between applications and VOs.

Multi-Cluster Monitoring: This component stores metrics, traces, and logs that constitute a set of observability signals from all the clusters in the NEPHELE ecosystem.

2.5 Edge / Cloud Resource Manager

At the cluster level, an individual Cluster Manager (CM) is activated for each edge or cloud cluster, overseeing the deployment of a segment of the application graph within its designated infrastructure. This involves executing local orchestration actions and gathering monitoring information. The components of the Cluster Resource Manager are analyzed in the following.

Cluster Scheduler: This component is responsible for implementing the actual scheduling of application nodes to the underlying infrastructure of each Kubernetes cluster considering key metrics. Therefore, to orchestrate the scheduling of the replicas of the application nodes to the edge and cloud clusters, we will formulate a multi-objective optimization problem that will compute a scheduling strategy to satisfy the systems’ intents.

Cluster Autoscaler: This component is responsible for deploying alongside the application the respective scaling mechanism that suits each application depending on the intent translation mechanism. Based on different application requirements, the Cluster Autoscaler instantiates the respective scaler (e.g., Horizontal Pod Autoscaler or AI-enabled scalers [3]) that scales the deployed services according to the selected metrics based also on real-time monitoring and prediction of the incoming workload.

Cluster Connectivity Manager: creates the necessary connectivity between clusters and enables IP reachability between Kubernetes pods and services. This way the application nodes communicate securely between them exposing only the necessary services for the inter-cluster communication utilizing e.g., VXLAN tunnels or VPNs.

Cluster Monitoring: collects default metrics for each node and each component in the cluster, but also enables the collection of custom metrics that are critical for understanding the unique aspects of an application’s performance.

2.6 VOSTack

The Virtual Object (VO), is the virtual counterpart/extension of IoT devices deployed on the premises of Edge/Cloud Clusters. The VOSTack is a lightweight software stack developed based on two different specifications, W3C Web of Things and Open Mobile Alliance Lightweight Machine-to-Machine, that stores the necessary information produced by IoT devices and therefore acts as a broker between the devices and an application graph. The purpose of the VOSTack is to solve three main challenges, namely; (i) Semantic abstraction: It provides a standard representation of a physical device for easier management, monitoring, and discovery of device resources, (ii) interoperability by implementing various communication protocols (HTTP, CoAP, MQTT), (iii) secure communication by deploying a set of authentication mechanisms (TLS, basic/bearer authentication), (iv) enriching the capabilities of resource-constrained devices by deploying a set of advanced functionalities (e.g compression, data series analysis, etc.) and (v) data modeling enabling the use of different data models.

3 NEPHELE Open-Source Approach

The NEPHELE consortium has implemented an open source strategy to foster a sustainable ecosystem and promote widespread adoption and exploitation of its technologies. By making its assets available under a business-friendly open source license (MIT), the consortium encourages collaboration, community contributions, and continuous improvement. Therefore, the project follows a practical open source strategy, grounded in the following pillars:

Continuous Landscaping: Building a community from the ground up around a new project is both a challenging and resource-intensive task, requiring significant effort and financial investment. Therefore, it’s essential to identify and engage with relevant existing open-source communities whenever possible, rather than reinventing the wheel. For instance, in the context of orchestrating Hyper Distributed Applications across the compute continuum, NEPHELE’s synergetic meta-orchestration framework utilizes the Open Source MANO⁶ (OSM) stack, following a system-of-systems approach. For the VOSTack, NEPHELE is following -among others- the Web of Things⁷ (WoT) standard. The Eclipse Thingweb^{TM8} node-wot is the official reference implementation of the Web of Things Scripting API written in the official specification. NEPHELE is taking upon the wot-py implementation and extending it with VOSTack features.

Open Source Best Practices: The NEPHELE open-source strategy prioritizes the adoption of best practices for open collaboration from the very start

⁶ <https://osm.etsi.org/>

⁷ <https://www.w3.org/WoT/>

⁸ <https://www.thingweb.io/>

of the project. All NEPHELE code, including code from Open Call projects, is hosted in the Eclipse Foundation Research Labs⁹ repository on servers based in Europe. This setup allows us to do robust IP and license management for the NEPHELE open-source outputs. It includes maintaining proper meta-information for repositories, ensuring compliance with outbound license requirements, and adhering to third-party license obligations. This framework not only facilitates open collaboration among project partners but also invites contributions from external parties, such as Open Call participants and other stakeholders.

Community Building: At this stage, it is crucial to engage with developer communities, particularly those identified during the landscaping process. Additionally, collaboration across all MetaOS projects within the EUCloud-EdgeIoT.eu initiative is encouraged through participation in various events and webinars. Plans are in place to enhance the exchange of ideas and to leverage each other’s open-source work, with the goal of collectively engaging developer communities. Building and sustaining a community around an open source project is a complex task and does not come for free. With the proposed strategy and according measures, we aim to increase the chances of sustaining such a community around the NEPHELE platform in the long term. In the final phase of the project, the consortium is working to transition its results into a community-driven open-source project under the Eclipse Foundation. It is important to emphasize that, in terms of sustainability and exploitation, this step marks the beginning of the project’s journey, not its end. This transition is just the first phase of NEPHELE’s path toward becoming a successful and thriving open-source initiative.

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⁹ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/nephele-project>